

BIM Data Delivery Checklist

The Project **Urban PERISCOPE** INTEGRATED/0918/0034 is co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund and the Republic of Cyprus through the Research Innovation Foundation.

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Abstract

This document presents the way the BIM data integrated into the 3d model must be exported and organised in order to be uploaded properly in the UP Platform.

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01_Historical Data

UP_XXX_XXX_DrawingsOfExistingConditions_SHR

UP_XXX_XXX_DrawingsOfExistingConditions_jpeg
UP_XXX_XXX_DrawingsOfExistingConditions_dwg
UP_XXX_XXX_DrawingsOfExistingConditions_pdf

UP_XXX_XXX_Conservation State Analysis_SHR

UP_CST-XXXXXX_doc
UP_CST-XXXXXX_pdf
UP_CST-XXXXXX_Jpeg

UP_XXX_XXX_PhotosOfExistingConditions_SHR

UP_XXX_XXX_IdentityData_SHR.xlsx
UP_XXX_XXX_BuildingDescription_SHR.doc
UP_XXX_XXX_ListedTab_SHR.jpeg

02_hBIM

UP_XXX_XXX_ExistingConditionsSurvey_SHR

UP_XXX_XXX_ExistingConditionsSurvey_jpeg
UP_XXX_XXX_ExistingConditionsSurvey_las

UP_XXX_XXX_3DGeometricalReconstruction_SHR

UP_XXX_XXX_3DGeometricalReconstruction_jpeg
UP_XXX_XXX_M3_SHR.fbx

UP_XXX_XXX_Ifc_SHR

UP_XXX_ARC_XXX_M3_ifc

UP_XXX_CYI_XXX_2dDrawings_SHR

UP_XXX_XXX_hBIMLibrary_SHR (*rfa files)

UP_XXX_XXX_BOQ_SHR.xlsx
UP_XXX_ARC_XXX_SheetList_SHR.xlsx
UP_XXX_ARC_XXX_M3_SHR.pdf

03_LCA

UP_XXX_XXX_LCA_pdf

04_NDT

UP_XXX_XXX_NDTReport_SHR

UP_XXX_XXX_NDTModel.jpeg

UP_XXX_XXX_NDTReport.jpeg

UP_XXX_XXX_NDTReport_doc

UP_XXX_XXX_NDTReport_pdf

UP_XXX_XXX_IR Thermographs.jpeg

UP_XXX_XXX_NDT_SHR.exe

UP_XXX_XXX_NDTWebStandalone_SHR.txt

05_Interactive visualization

UP_XXX_XXX_Rederings_SHR

UP_XXX_7D.01_CYI_XXX_360Rederings_SHR

UP_XXX_XXX_RD_SHR.exe

UP_XXX_XXX_RDWebStandalone_SHR.txt